

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

USE OF MINERAL DUSTS GENERATED IN STONE QUARRIES

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Abstract

The negative impact of stone quarry to the environment in Absheron Peninsula, elimination of the impacts, modification of stone dust and using them in improving asphalt surface and increasing service life.

Keywords: stone quarry, stone dust, oil acid

The increase in the demand for building materials on the Absheron Peninsula leads to the proliferation of stone quarries. For this reason, the dust raised during strong winds increases the damage to the environment, human health, flora and fauna. At the same time, every newly opened stone quarry makes the land allocated for agriculture useless and unsuitable for future use. One of the main solutions to this problem is to minimize the creation of new quarries and speed up the reclamation process. For this purpose, stone powders can be used as a second raw material in asphalt pavement as an economically efficient material.

The advantage of this method is the acceleration of the reclamation of stone quarries, the prevention of the creation of new stone quarries, and at the same time the acquisition of economically profitable raw materials. It is known that the asphalt coating is exposed to water, temperature changes, and breaks down faster than the expected service life. For this purpose, mineral powders taken from mines are activated and applied to the asphalt concrete coating. Activating powders means increasing their hydrophobicity, thereby increasing the asphalt's water resistance, that is, the penetration of

rainwater into the asphalt layer is reduced to a minimum, its porosity decreases, and its service life in a wide temperature range increases.

However, the properties of mineral powders may be different in different regions, and in this regard, powders taken from different mines are used. Experiments were carried out with stone dust taken from Garadag and Guzdek regions for the purpose of research on the Absheron Peninsula. Hydrophobicity of stone dust is obtained on the basis of fatty acids synthesized in laboratory conditions.

Different results were obtained by synthesizing corn, sunflower, soybean, cotton and palm fatty acids with various vegetable oils as stone dust activators. Of the acids mentioned above, corn and sunflower fatty acids showed higher results.

To carry out the work, a heater, a mechanical stirrer, a 3-necked flask and a thermometer are taken. Corn oil is poured into the reactor and heated to 65-70⁰ C with constant stirring, and the temperature is raised to 90-95⁰ C by gradually adding 30% NaOH solution. At this time, the hydrolysis process takes place, and distilled water is added as foam gradually forms to speed up the process.

At the next stage, the fatty acid is separated from the water by pouring it into a separating funnel and is washed 3 times in hot water and evaporated at 90-95°C for one hour. Synthesized vegetable fatty acid is subjected to infrared spectroscopy analysis and absorption bands are determined. The physico-chemical properties of the obtained fatty acid are analyzed. The synthesized fatty acid is homogenized with ground stone powder and poured into a chemical beaker filled with distilled water and the homogenous mixture is spread over it. Hydrophobicity is checked by keeping it quiet for a day.

To examine the surface activity of the powder, the beaker is moved back and forth for 1 second and repeated 10 times. If the stone dust did not settle to the bottom of the water after the process or did not cloud the water, this indicates that its hydrophilicity has decreased to a minimum, that is, its hydrophobicity has increased. Laboratory studies of a homogeneous mixture of acid and stone powder show that the activated

stone powder remains on the water surface for more than 10 days and does not sink to the bottom of the water and does not cloud the water. As a result, the application of activated stone dust in asphalt pavement increases its service life due to the increase of surface activity.

References

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STUDY OF PENTYL BROMIDE COMPLEX OF AMIDOAMINE OF SUNFLOWER ACIDS AS A CORROSION INHIBITOR

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Abstract

The protection of metal-containing equipment from corrosion is one of the urgent problems in today's rapidly developing technological environment. This problem is more related to CO₂ corrosion of steel equipment and pipelines in the production and processing of oil and gas, which is the basis of the oil sector [1,2]. Although the corrosion process cannot be completely prevented, there are various ways to significantly reduce its rate. The most effective and easy to use is the use of corrosion inhibitors. [3-6]

Keywords: CO₂ corrosion, inhibitors, amidoamine, triethylenetetraamine, sunflower oil acids

For this purpose, an amidoamine based on sunflower oil acids and triethylenetetraamine was synthesized. In the next step, an inorganic complex of the resulting amide (N-6) is synthesized. using pentyl bromide (C₅H₁₁Br) as alkyl halides. The reaction is preferably carried out in a molar ratio of 1:1, with stirring at 80-81°C for 3 hours. The resulting complex is dark yellow, viscous, readily soluble in isopropyl alcohol. The yield of the complex obtained as a result of the

reaction is 95%. The structure of the resulting complex was confirmed by IR spectroscopy.

The effect of the complex on the kinetics of corrosion of steel in 1% NaCl solution in water saturated with CO₂ on steel surfaces was carried out on the potentiometer "ACM Instruments GILL AC no-1197" at a temperature of 50°C, a pressure of 0.9 bar, for 20 hours. A graphical representation of the results obtained is shown in Figure 1.